

Amorphous Core Distribution Transformer with Improved Efficiency and Low Loss for Power Sector Application

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ABSTRACT:

The amorphous transformer (AMTD) is an energy-efficient transformer that minimizes both airborne pollutants and the amount of energy required to create power. This research investigates the use of amorphous material in transformer construction rather than the usual silicon steel core. It outperforms silicon steel in terms of magnetic characteristics. Because of its high resistivity and low thickness, adopting amorphous as a transformer core instead of a traditional transformer can eliminate 70% of transformer no load losses. When deciding which transform to install and use in the electrical network, the total prices of silicon steel and amorphous steel are considered. The total owed cost (TOC) of any specific transformer is calculated by discounting future transformer losses (losses from both load and no load) to present value and leveling them across the transformer's lifetime. The characteristics of amorphous and conventional electrical cold-rolled grain-oriented (CRGO) materials were evaluated. Amorphous metal is a special type of alloy with an irregular molecular arrangement rather than a well-organized crystalline structure. Amorphous metal can be utilized for the transformer core to increase transformer efficiency. The material's increased magnetic characteristics and physical dimensions lead to much lower hysteresis and eddy current losses. Using amorphous metal cores can minimize transformer core loss by more than 60 percent. High power-density transformers are in high demand in many applications where weight and available space are severely constrained, such as power electronics. While electromagnetic device weights and sizes normally decrease at higher frequencies, core loss may increase considerably.

Keywords: amorphous, AMTD, silicon steel core, CRGO, crystalline structure, transformer design.

INTRODUCTION

Transformers are most important components of any electrical circuit or power system. The "transformer core" is by far one of the most significant sections of the transformer, aside from the "transformer windings," which are secondary. This component is required for the transformer's functionality. Regardless of kind of transformer employed in a given power system, choice of core or the material used for the core has a considerable influence on the system's efficiency. The continuous process that occurs in a transformer's core as electricity travels through its primary windings is known as "magnetization." The core begins to magnetize as soon as current runs through primary winding, dependent on "number of turns" in winding. It then continues to magnetize and demagnetize itself, depending on magnetizing characteristics & saturation time of the core material.

The amorphous metal is not crystalline, unlike silicon steel. The atoms of amorphous metal are organized differently than in silicon steel. This can be demonstrated in schematic given in Figures 1a, b. [1].

Figure 1a. Crystalline Silicon Steel [1] Figure 1b. Non-Crystalline Amorphous Metal [1]

When a magnetic field is applied, the amorphous metal's randomness creates a smaller proportion than that of silicon steel. As a result, hysteresis losses in the amorphous transformer are minimized, resulting in a greater reduction in no-load losses than the silicon steel core transformer [1]. Amorphous metal laminate has lower losses for eddy current than silicon steel core transformer due to its exceptionally thin nature. Thin laminations result in minimal eddy current losses and resistance between laminations. New transformers with amorphous metal cores lose 70-80% less energy in the core than silicon steel core transformers due to lower hysteresis and eddy current losses [2]. Table 1 summarizes the load & no-load losses for silicon steel and amorphous transformers of various sizes. Figure 2 depicts the performance of silicon and amorphous steel in an impressed oil transformer with a capacity of 1000 KVA. It is clear that at various load currents, the AMT transformer efficiency exceeds that of silicon steel. As seen in Figure 3, employing an amorphous transformer saves electricity at all sizes.

Table 1. No Load Losses & Load Losses for Amorphous & silicon Steel [1] Transformer [2]

Silicon Steel			AMTD	
Transformer Size KVA	No Load Losses W	Load losses W	No Load Losses W	Load Losses W
50	170	870	43	910
100	290	1500	75	1580
200	480	2600	120	2730
500	960	5150	240	5410
1000	1700	10300	450	10300

Because distribution transformers (DTs) are among the biggest groupings of equipment in an electrical network, DT losses account for a considerable proportion of total network losses [3]. Electric utilities and industry are always seeking for solutions to reduce operational expenses and energy losses. The most efficient distribution transformers, which are in continuous operation, lose around 2 to 4% of the power they transmit. Distribution transformers' loads vary during the day and night, although their capacity is usually set to accommodate the maximum demand during the day. However, the maximum demand on DT, which occurs just a few hours per day, is typically far more than the average load. Reducing network losses for any utility is heavily reliant on all-day efficiency or efficiency at lighter loads, which takes into consideration the distribution transformer's average loading [4].

Fig 2. AMT and Silicon Steel transformer Performance 11000KVA [4]

LOSSES IN DISTRIBUTION TRANSFORMERS

A distribution transformer has two sorts of losses: load losses, which are determined by the transformer's loading, and no-load losses, which are independent of the load. When a transformer has a poor load factor, no-load losses might make up a sizable amount of its total losses. The distribution transformer design emphasizes reducing these losses while maintaining transformer performance. By using higher-grade electrical steel cores and enhancing design, the principal component of losses no-load loss—can be reduced. Using higher-grade CRGO laminations can significantly reduce no-load loss. In comparison to CRGO core losses, the development of Amorphous Metal Distribution Transformers (AMDT) provides an even higher decrease in transformer core losses [5,6].

Amorphous core material (AM) has lower hysteresis and eddy current loss than typical CRGO due to its high permeability, which is driven by its random grain and magnetic domain structure. Another issue contributing to DT's decline is the use of impure and secondhand CRGO. The thicker layer, along with the high resistivity of the amorphous material, reduce eddy current losses. The laminations are made up of thin ribbons, and the sheet thickness is around 0.025-0.030 mm, or one-

tenth that of the CRGO. Amorphous core transformers reduce no-load losses by 70-80% when compared to CRGO core transformers with the same rating [7,8].

Table 2. The Typical Comparative Figures of No Load Losses of AMDT and CRGO Core are Given Below [8]

Transformer size (kVA)	AMDT	CRGO DT	% Loss reduction
100	65	145	55
250	110	300	63
400	170	430	60

Figure 3. Amorphous Core [7]

Figure 4. CRGO Core [7]

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Because of the mechanical properties of amorphous ribbons, amorphous cores are often formed as wounded, one-sided cutting structures. This method makes it easier to build electric windings and ensures that air gaps within a core are properly located. Amorphous transformers have a 3- or 5-limb core structure and are available in single- or three-phase configuration [9]. The greatest capacity of currently manufactured amorphous transformers is 10 MVA. Because amorphous ribbons have a lower saturation induction than silicon steel cores, their cross-section is bigger. The weight and size of the transformer grow as a result. Determining conductor's cross-section area and ferromagnetic material's cross-section core are critical phases in transformer design [10]. These areas are determined using estimated values for winding space factor, stacking factor, peak flux density, & full-load RMS current density in windings. The current density depends on whether transformers operate intermittently or continuously. The space factor is the ratio of core window area to total conductor cross-sectional area. The stacking factor is determined by ratio of ferromagnetic material's cross-sectional area to the total cross-sectional area of the core. Grain-oriented silicon sheets are generally 0.9 mm or thicker [11]. This value is lower with the amorphous alloy than with conventional silicon iron. Because of its thinness and uneven surface, amorphous materials have a space factor of just 80%, as opposed to 95% for silicon iron. For example, amorphous design with square sections of core (AMDTs) is depicted in sectional view below.

Core losses in CRGO = (specific core loss in watt per Kg.) CRGO x mass of CRGO in frame
 Core losses in amorphous = (specific core loss in watt per Kg.) Amorphous x mass of amorphous in frame
 Copper losses in windings = i^2R

Amorphous core transformers have a far lower no-load loss than conventional transformers with silicon steel cores. It is the result of amorphous ribbons' very low energy loss and their short thickness, which significantly minimizes eddy current flow. The decrease in no-load loss in amorphous transformers is predicted to be 70-80% [12].

Figure 5. Amorphous Core with Square section [11]

SIGNIFICANCE AND INNOVATION

It is probable that the range of power electronics and power systems will follow trend of using high frequency & lowering the size of the power transformer in order to achieve high power and efficiency. The drive toward high frequency operation & downsizing of power electronic systems has substantially accelerated development of low power loss, high permeability magnetic materials. The discovery of amorphous metal materials has made it possible to attain greater efficiencies and smaller transformers, as indicated by their unique features and some research in this field. However, little effort has been done to determine the magnetic characteristics of these materials and, as a result, define how they behave.

The transformer industry has developed Amorphous Metal Distribution Transformers (AMDT), which are expected to be extremely efficient transformers. Among the providers, ABB may be the first to deploy an amorphous steel core in an amorphous core distribution transformer. ABB's ultra-low loss design solution for AMDTs is a perfect example of minimizing loss while increasing efficiency. Instead of employing regular grain orientated (RGO) silicon steel, they build using a specific alloy whose atomic structure is chaotic or unpredictable. Because of the well-aligned and organized grain structure of RGO, magnetization cycles encounter high resistance, increasing core losses. This amorphous material core allows for the same high permeability but comparatively low resistance to magnetization cycles, resulting in lower core losses due to its more irregular structure or atom alignment. Transformers with amorphous metal cores provide a technical advantage. When compared to Regular Grain Oriented (RGO) transformers, AM-based transformers have much reduced losses at no load. According to one research and test, common liquid-filled transformer designs can have losses as low as 70%. This is displayed in the table. Transformers made of amorphous metal are also efficient and function best when the power frequencies contain harmonics or integral multiples. Power waveform distortion, or disrupted current & voltage waveforms that cause harmonics in circuit, happens in presence of non-linear loads, such as spinning machinery. This is likely to lead to transformer losses and reduced power quality. Amorphous Metal Core Based Transformers (AMDT) decrease these harmonic losses. This reduces operational energy consumption in a variety of inductive & resistive loads. Reduced losses from amorphous metal (AM) cause a transformer to utilize much less energy during its lifespan. Furthermore, AM's non-crystalline structure allows for simple magnetization, and no-load core losses are greatly minimized thanks to its low thickness and high resistivity [13]. Because to molecular nature of its amorphous core, Power Star SO-LO smart transformer meets or exceeds 2021 EU Eco Design Directive Standards, as

indicated in tables below. This is because, unlike the rigid structure found in silicon steel, metal atoms form a random pattern. This, along with the ribbon's narrowest 0.025mm and high electrical resistivity, results in decreased hysteresis losses as less energy is wasted during supply current's fixation and demagnetization cycles.

Table 3. EU Eco Design Directive Standards

RATED POWER (kVA)	CONVENTIONAL CRGO DISTRIBUTION TRANSFORMER			2021EU ECODESIGN DIRECTIVE STANDARDS				
	Load [W]	Losses [W]	No Load Losses (core losses)[W]	Impedance [%]	Load [W]	Losses [W]	No Load Losses(core losses) [W]	Impedance[%]
315	5000		770	4	2800		324	4
500	7200		1000	4	3900		459	4
800	10500		1400	6	4600		585	4.5
1000	13000		1700	6	7600		693	4.5
1600	20000		2600	6	12000		1080	4.5
2000	2600		3100	6	15000		1305	5
2500	3200		3500	6	18500		1575	5

CONCLUSIONS

It is clear that the molecular and/or atomic structure of ferromagnetic Fe-based amorphous metal materials can vary somewhat, causing changes in mechanical and magnetic properties. We may analyze the amorphous metals research undertaken by different researcher's by changing their composition or atomic scale structure, as proven by diverse research works presented below. Purchasing a more expensive, higher-efficiency transformer over a cheaper, lower-efficiency transformer will result in significant cost savings over length of a transformer's lifetime. Because AMDTs do not have lower load losses than CRGO core DTs, they may be used in villages where peak load occurs momentarily and the DT is normally lightly loaded. Harmonics were not taken into consideration while computing load losses. When it comes to decreasing load loss under harmonic settings, AMDTs are well known for their good reaction. This is an additional advantage of AMDTs in the present distribution system context, where nonlinear loads are increasing.

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